

1,4-Dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride a new and efficient catalyst for the synthesis of 14-aryl-14*H*-dibenzo[*a,j*]xanthenes in water as solvent

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Abstract : A new and green procedure for the synthesis of 14-aryl-14*H*-dibenzo[*a,j*]xanthenes through one-pot condensation of naphthalen-2-ol with benzaldehydes in the presence of 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride as catalyst in water as a solvent is described.

Keywords : Xanthene, 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride, aldehyde, β -naphthol, water solvent.

Introduction

The synthesis of xanthenes, especially benzoxanthenes, has emerged as a powerful tool in organic synthesis due to their wide range of biological and therapeutic properties such as antibacterial¹, antiviral² and anti-inflammatory activities³, as well as in photodynamic therapy^{4,5} and for antagonism of the paralyzing action of zoxazolamine^{6,7} and various methods have been reported for their synthesis⁸⁻¹⁰. However, these methods suffer from one or more disadvantages such as a long reaction time, low yield, use of toxic solvents, requirement of excess of reagents/catalysts, laborious workup procedures, and harsh reaction conditions. Thus, the development of an environmentally benign methodology for the synthesis of benzoxanthene derivatives is of great interest. In continuation of my investigations on *N*-halo compounds¹¹ here I report the use of 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride which is a new and environmentally friendly catalyst for synthesis of xanthenes in water.

Results and discussion

1,4-Dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride (Fig. 1) is easily and quantitatively prepared by treatment of chlorine gas with 1,4-diazabicyclo[2,2,2]octane in CHCl_3 at room temperature. It is a homogenous solid and soluble in water and it can be kept for months in a

vessel without losing its activity. It did not release chlorine atom during storage, as its analysis after two months showed no loss of chlorine atom. It had no offensive odor of chlorine or amine. It is inexpensive and DABCO is recovered, rechlorinated and reused several times in reactions¹²⁻¹⁷.

Fig. 1

Here I report the use of 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride as a more robust and efficient catalyst in a one-pot synthesis of the 14-aryl-14*H*-dibenzo[*a,j*]xanthene derivatives by reaction of β -naphthol (**2**) with different benzaldehydes in excellent yields (90–99%) in water as solvent (Scheme 1 and Table 1). The use of water as a solvent makes the reaction interesting from both an economic and environmental point of view.

As shown in the table, the reactions occurred within 35–67 min. The results indicate that the most effective conversion occurred when a substrate/1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride mol ratio of 1 : 0.1 was used. Longer reaction times were required when

Scheme 1

Table-1 (contd.)

Entry	Aldehyde	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b	m.p. (°C) ^c					
1		45	95	182 (183)	15		35	99	204 (205)
2		55	94	286 (287)	16		38	96	227 (228)
3		58	95	215 (215)	<p>^aAll products are known, and they were characterized by IR and NMR spectral analysis, and compared with authentic samples. ^bYields of isolated products. ^cMelting points of compounds are consistent with reported values¹⁰ (in parentheses).</p> <p>lower amounts of 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]-octane bis chloride were employed. It is important to note that no 14-aryl-4H-dibenzo[a,j]xanthenes derivatives were obtained when the reactions were performed in the absence of 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride.</p> <p>A reaction mechanism has been proposed. The reaction likely proceeds via initial formation of intermediate (4). The oxonium species (5) is then formed on reaction with β-naphthol, which then undergoes dehydration to offer the desired product (3) (Scheme 2).</p> <p>The positive features of the present method are : (i) ease of operation; (ii) facile recycling of the DABCO; (iii) excellent yields; (iv) environmental consciousness : no organic solvent is used in the reaction and only a small amount is needed for the workup.</p> <p>Experimental</p> <p>All the starting materials were purchased from Fluka and Merck. The products were known compounds and they were identified by comparison of their physical data, IR and NMR spectra with those of authentic samples. Melting points were determined using a Mettler FP 5 apparatus and were uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were measured at 300 MHz on a JEOL spectrometer with tetramethylsilane (Me₄Si) as an internal reference and CDCl₃ as the solvent. IR spectra were recorded on Pye-</p>				
4		67	92	225 (227)					
5		50	94	295 (296)					
6		50	95	192 (190)					
7		61	91	235 (238)					
8		60	91	257 (259)					
9		65	92	291 (293)					
10		65	90	212 (213)					
11		62	90	310 (312)					
12		40	96	94 (93)					
13		43	98	199 (199)					
14		40	98	141 (140)					

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Unicam SP 1100 spectrophotometer. Elemental analysis was performed on a LECO 250 instrument.

A mixture of the aldehyde (1 mmol), β -naphthol (2 mmol) and 1,4-dichloro-1,4-diazoniabicyclo[2,2,2]octane bis chloride (0.1 mmol, 0.0254 g) was stirred in water as solvent at 50 °C for the appropriate time according to Table 1. Completion of the reaction was indicated by

TLC. The reaction was cooled to room temperature, Et₂O (10 mL) was added to reaction mixture and was washed with solution of 1% aq. HCl (1 × 10 mL). The aqueous layer 1 was separated and the organic layer was washed with 3% aq. NaHCO₃ (1 × 10 mL) and water (1 × 10 mL) respectively. The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered and evaporated to dryness under reduced

Scheme 2

pressure to afford product then recrystallized from ethyl alcohol.

Regeneration of 1,4-diazabicyclo[2,2,2]octane :

The aqueous layer **1** from the above procedure was further treated with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution (2 × 10 mL) and 1,4-diazabicyclo[2,2,2]octane (DABCO) was extracted with ether (3 × 10 mL). The ether layer was dried over MgSO₄, and evaporated to give pure 1,4-diazabicyclo[2,2,2]octane (0.011 g, 95%), which can be chlorinated and reused several times.

Selected characterization data :

14-(3-Fluorophenyl)-14H-dibenzo[a,j]xanthene (Table 1, entry 8) : Brown solid : m.p. 257 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3152, 1593, 1404, 1240, 1205, 1068, 817, 747; ¹H NMR

(300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 6.51 (1H, s), 6.72–8.28 (16H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 38.1, 112.7 and 90, 113.0 (JC–F 21.5 Hz), 114.6 and 115.5 (JC–F 21.5 Hz), 117.8, 119.1, 123.0, 124.31 and 125.34 (JC–F 2.8 Hz), 124.2, 127.9, 128.9, 129.1, 130.7 and 131.2 (JC–F 8.3 Hz), 131.5, 131.7 (JC–F 19.4 Hz), 147.4, 147.8 (JC–F 6.2 Hz), 149.2, 161.5, 165.1; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₁₇FO : C, 86.15; H, 4.55; F, 5.05. Found : C, 86.09; H, 4.59, F, 5.06.

14-(2-Nitrophenyl)-14H-dibenzo[a,j]xanthene (Table 1, entry 9) : Yellow solid : m.p. 291 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3400, 3048, 1598, 1529, 1352, 1241, 1141, 810, 748; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.53 (1H, s), 7.10–8.66 (16H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 33.9, 118.0, 118.4, 124.0, 124.6, 125.0, 125.9, 127.4, 128.2, 129.4,

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129.5, 129.9, 131.5, 132.7, 132.5, 134.5, 142.3, 147.7, 150.1; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{17}NO_3$: C, 80.38; H, 4.25; N, 3.47. Found : C, 80.45; H, 4.31, N, 3.39.

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